

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
KANAMYCIN & CEPHALEXIN BY USING RP- HPLC**P. Swathanthra Babu^{1*}, S. Bhayalata², Chaitanya Bangari³, Dr.M.B.Venkatapathi Raju⁴¹Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.

Article Received: March 2020

Accepted: April 2020

Published: May 2020

Abstract:

A novel method were recognized for simultaneous estimation of Kanamycin and Cephalexin by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were effectively developed for the separation of Kanamycin and Cephalexin by by means of SYMMETRYC18 column (4.6×150mm)5μ, flow rate were 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio were (70:30 v/v)methanol: phosphate buffer(KH₂PO₄and K₂HPO₄) pH 3 (pH were accustomed with orthophosphoric acid),detection wavelength were 258nm. The instrument utilizing was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.403 mins and 3.907mins. The % purity of Kanamycin and Cephalexin were establish to be 100.27% and 99.87% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Kanamycin and Cephalexin such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 2294, 1.27 and 4891 and 1.03, the resolution were found to be 8.67. The analytical method were validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study n Kanamycin and Cephalexin were found in concentration range of 50μg-250μg and 5μg-50μg and correlation coefficient (r²) were found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery were found to be 99.56% and 99.48%, %RSD for repeatability were 0.27 and 0.40, % RSD for intermediate precision were 0.27 and 0.94 respectively. The precision study were precise, robust, and repeatable.LOD value were 2.17 and 6.60, and LOQ value were 0.032 and 0.1125 respectively.

Keywords: Kanamycin , Cephalexin , precise, robust, and repeatable.**Corresponding author:****P.Swathanthra Babu,**

Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162.

p.swathanthrababu@gmail.com / pharmamadhuphd@gmail.com

9603359175 / 7799263656

QR code

Please cite this article in press Swathanthra Babu et al, *The Analytical Method Development And Validation For The Simultaneous Estimation Of Kanamycin & Cephalexin By Using RP- HPLC.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Kanamycin (also known as kanamycin A) is an aminoglycoside bacteriocidal antibiotic, available in oral, intravenous, and intramuscular forms, and used to treat a wide variety of infections. Kanamycin is isolated from the bacterium *Streptomyces kanamyceticus* and its most commonly used form is kanamycin sulphate [10].

Cephalexin is the first of the first generation cephalosporins. This antibiotic contains a beta lactam and a dihydrothiazide. Cephalexin is used to treat a number of susceptible bacterial infections through inhibition of cell wall synthesis [10].

The analysis of Kanamycin and Cephalexin by simultaneous estimation by RP-HPLC. Spectrophotometer, HPLC and HPTLC are the reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form[1]. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development for the simultaneous estimation of Kanamycin and Cephalexin in pharmaceutical dosage form. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous analysis of Kanamycin and Cephalexin. The developed technique determination be validated conferring to ICH guidelines.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY: [2-9]

List of chemicals and standards used

S.No	Chemicals	Manufacturer Name	Grade
1.	Water	Merck	HPLC grade
2.	Methanol	Merck	HPLC grade
3.	Acetonitrile	Merck	HPLC grade
4.	Ortho phosphoric acid	Merck	G.R
5.	KH ₂ PO ₄	Merck	G.R
6.	K ₂ HPO ₄	Merck	G.R
7.	0. 22µ Nylon filter	Advanced lab	HPLC grade
8.	0.45µ filter paper	Millipore	HPLC grade
9.	Kanamycin and cephalixin	In - House	In- House

List of instruments used

S.No	Instrument name	Model number	Soft ware	Manufacturers Name
1	HPLC-auto sampler – UV detector	Separation module2695, UV.detector2487	Empower-software version-2	Waters
2	U.V double beam spectrometer	UV 3000+	U.V win soft ware	Lab India
3	Digital weighing balance(sensitivity 5mg)	ER 200A	-	Ascotet
4	pH meter	AD 102U	-	ADWA
5	Sonicator	SE60US	-	Enertech

Procedure:**Preparation of phosphate buffer:**

2.95 grams of KH_2PO_4 and 5.45 grams of K_2HPO_4 was weighed and taken into a 1000ml beaker, dissolved and diluted to 1000ml with HPLC water and pH was adjusted to 3 with orthophosphoric acid. The resulting solution was sonicated and filtered.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Mix a mixture of above buffer 300 ml (30%) and 700 ml of methanol (HPLC grade-70%) and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.22 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluents preparation

Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of the individual kanamycin standard preparation:

10 mg of kanamycin working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 1.5ml from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of the individual cephalixin standard preparation:

1 mg of cephalixin working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 3 ml from the above

Assay calculation

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{dilution sample}}{\text{dilution of standard}} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. wt}}{Lc} \times 100$$

Where: Avg.wt = average weight of tablets, P= Percentage purity of working standard
LC= Label Claim of kanamycin mg/ml.

stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of the kanamycin and cephalixin standard and sample solution

Sample solution preparation:

10mg of kanamycin and 1mg cephalixin tablet powder were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and making volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette 10ml of the above stock solution into a 100ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Standard solution preparation:

10 mg kanamycin and 1mg cephalixin working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 1ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

10 μ L of the blank, standard and sample were injected into the chromatographic system and areas for the kanamycin and cephalixin peaks were used for calculating the % assay by using the formulae.

System suitability

- Tailing factor for the peaks due to kanamycin and cephalixin in standard solution should not be more than 1.5.
- Theoretical plates for the kanamycin and cephalixin peaks in standard solution should not be less than 2000.

	Trail -1	Trail 2	Trail 3	Trail 4	Trail 5 optimised method
Mobile phase	MeOH: H ₂ O (50:50%v/v)	ACN: H ₂ O (50:50%v/v)	ACN: pH 6.8 buffer (50:50 % v/v)	ACN: pH 3 buffer (65:35% v/v)	ACN: pH 3 buffer (70: 30 % v/v)
Diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent

Flow rate	1ml/min	1.0ml per min	1.0 ml per min	1.0 ml per min	1.0 ml per min
Column	Symmetry, C18 4.6x150mm, 5 μ m	Zodiacsil C18 4.6x150mm 5 μ m	Hypersil RPC8 4.5x150mm 5.0 μ m	Zodiac sil RPC18 4.6x250mm 5 μ m	zodiac silRP C18 4.6x250mm 3.0 μ m
Detector wavelength	236nm	240nm	240nm	240 nm	240 nm
Column oven	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient
Injection volume	10 μ l	20 μ l	20 μ l	20 μ l	20 μ l
Running time	10min	8.0 min	10 min	5min	10min

Validation parameters such as specificity, Linearity, Range, Accuracy, Precision, Repeatability, Intermediate Precision, Detection Limit, Quantitation Limit, Robustness also studied⁵⁻¹⁰.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Trial-1: Chromatogram showing trial-1 injection

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Peak1	4.374	1309146	89140		0.92	1992	1
2	Peak2	5.057	4562063	195176	1.35	1.23	1037	1

Observation:

The trial doesn't show any peaks in the chromatogram, so more trials were required for obtaining peaks.

Trial - 2 Chromatogram showing trial-2 injection

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1		4.374	1789705	101899			1530	1
2		5.057	5319297	210444	1.21		942	1

Observation:

In this trial only cephalixin peak only eluted, still more trials were required for both peaks.

Trial-3 Chromatogram showing trial-3 injection

Peak Results

Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	4.947	1589459	82371			745	1
2	5.511	4468664	160090			976	1

Observation

In this trial both Kanamycin and cephalixin were eluted but there is no proper resolution. Still more trials were required for better resolution in peaks.

Trial-4 Chromatogram showing trial-4 injections

Peak Results

Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	4.971	7288452	448684		1.10	2059	1
2	6.222	2333490	102164	2.48	1.04	1966	1

Observation:

The separation was good; peak shape was good, still more trials were required to reduce the retention times of peaks.

Trial -5 (optimised method): Chromatogram showing trial-5 injection

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Kanamycin	3.516	467064	51548		1.47	3830	1
2	cephalexin	4.869	321623	24643		1.44	3253	1

Observation

The separation was good, peak shape was good, so we conclude that there is no required for reduce the retention times of peaks, so it is taken as final method.

Method Development:

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10 μ g/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of kanamycin and cephalexin was obtained and the isobestic point of kanamycin and cephalexin showed absorbance's maxima at 240 nm. The spectrums are shown in Fig.

The chromatographic method development for the simultaneous estimation of kanamycin and cephalixin were optimized by several trials for various parameters as different column, flow rate and mobile phase, finally the following chromatographic method was selected for the separation and quantification of kanamycin and cephalixin in API and pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC method.

Optimized chromatographic conditions for simultaneous estimations of Kanamycin and cephalixin by RP-HPLC method

Chromatogram showing blank preparation (mobile phase)

Assay calculation for kanamycin and cephalixin

The assay study was performed for the kanamycin and cephalixin. Each three injections of sample and standard were injected into chromatographic system. The chromatograms are shown in Fig. And results below

Chromatogram showing assay of sample injection-1,2,3

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.516	518397	57148		1.47	3828	1
2	Kanamycin	4.870	790333	57188	4.56	1.56	3149	1
3	cephalexin	3.514	518072	56951		1.51	3789	2
4	Kanamycin	4.867	790053	56762	4.52	1.58	3118	2
5	cephalexin	3.514	521948	57230		1.50	3861	3
6	Kanamycin	4.864	795078	57114	4.53	1.61	3112	3

Chromatogram showing assay of standard injection -1,2,3.

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.549	508691	56817		1.42	3923	2
2	kanamycin	4.981	747698	55296	4.79	1.46	3149	2
3	cephalexin	3.520	519881	57981		1.46	3946	3
4	kanamycin	4.878	741850	57648	4.71	1.43	3348	3
5	cephalexin	3.520	519881	57981		1.46	3946	3
6	kanamycin	4.878	741850	57648	4.71	1.43	3348	3

The retention time of kanamycin and cephalixin was found to be 2.406 mins and 3.973mins respectively. The system suitability parameters for kanamycin and cephalixin such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 2294, 1.27 and 4891, 1.03. Resolution was 8.67. The % purity kanamycin and cephalixin in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 98.24 and 100.27% respectively.

VALIDATION REPORT:

Specificity:

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there is any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The study was performed by injecting blank. The chromatograms are shown in Fig below

Chromatogram showing standard injection

The specificity test was performed for Kanamycin and cephalalexin. It was found that there was no interference of impurities in retention time of analytical peak.

Linearity:

The linearity study was performed for the concentration of 50 ppm to 250 ppm and 5ppm to 25 ppm level. Each level was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each level was used for calculation of correlation coefficient. The chromatograms are shown below and Calibration graph for CEF and KAN are shown .

Chromatograms showing linearity level-1 to level 5 (50ppm-250 ppm)

Linearity Results for Cephalaxin:

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	50 ppm	471543
2	II	100 ppm	656277
3	III	150 ppm	794999
4	IV	200 ppm	946124
5	V	250 ppm	1002139
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	5ppm	56472
2	II	10 ppm	73841
3	III	15ppm	92655
4	IV	20ppm	111541
5	V	25ppm	130567
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Cephalexin² = 0.999

Linearity Results for Kanamycin:

Showing calibration graph for Kanamycin

Kanamycin $r^2 = 0.999$

OVERLAY DIAGRAM

The linearity study was performed for concentration range of 50.µg-250µg and 5µg-50µg of kanamycin and cephalalexin and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999 and 0.999.(NLT 0.999).

Accuracy:

The accuracy study was performed for 80%, 100% and 120 % for kanamycin and cephalalexin. Each level was injected in triplicate into chromatographic system. The area of each level was used for calculation of % recovery. Chromatograms are shown in Fig. and results are tabulated in below

Chromatograms showing accuracy-80% injection-1,2,3

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.515	852858	90288		1.79	3645	1
2	kanamycin	4.855	1425312	96264	4.32	1.99	2850	1
3	cephalexin	3.516	854502	90471		1.74	3685	2
4	kanamycin	4.856	1425604	96724	4.34	1.98	2844	2
5	Febuxostat	3.515	853960	89576		1.78	3629	3
6	kanamycin	4.857	1424941	96279	4.32	1.98	2847	3

Accuracy -100%

Chromatogram showing accuracy -100% injection-1,2,3.

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.521	1119197	116736		1.84	3637	1
2	kanamycin	4.863	1499388	100942	4.32	2.04	2860	1
3	cephalexin	3.517	1119910	117508		1.80	3643	2
4	kanamycin	4.860	1500972	100747	4.33	2.02	2833	2
5	cephalexin	3.515	1118239	117424		1.86	3627	3
6	kanamycin	4.859	1499296	100606	4.31	2.03	2852	3

Accuracy 120%

. Chromatogram showing accuracy -120 % injection-1,2,3.

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.517	1038871	108527		1.87	3623	1
2	Kanamycin	4.853	2024658	132459	4.24	2.09	2678	1
3	cephalexin	3.516	1038553	107528		1.86	3611	2
4	Kanamycin	4.852	2021564	131567	4.22	2.09	2705	2
5	cephalexin	3.516	1037242	108249		1.89	3631	3
6	Kanamycin	4.853	2021860	131786	4.23	2.09	2694	3

Showing accuracy results for Cephalexin

%Concentration (at specification level)	Average area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean recovery
50%	7371253	5	4.96	99.91%	99.56%
100%	14634226.7	10	9.98	99.18%	
150%	2243270.7	15	15.02	99.60%	

Showing accuracy results for Kanamycin

%Concentration (at specification level)	Average area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean recovery
50%	484733	0.5	0.99	99.53%	99.47%
100%	967998	1.0	1.05	99.38%	
150%	145437	1.5	1.495	99.52%	

The accuracy study was performed for % recovery of Kanamycin and cephalexin. The % recovery was found to be 99.18% and 99.91% respectively (NLT 98% and NMT 102%)

Precision:**Repeatability**

The precision study was performed for five injections of kanamycin and cephalexin. Each standard injection was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each Standard injection was used for calculation of % RSD. The chromatograms are shown in Fig. and results are tabulated below.

. Chromatograms showing precision injections-1 to 5

Peak Name : Kanamycin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu V \cdot sec$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Kanamycin	4.864	787229	56504	3081.3	1.6	4.5
2	Kanamycin	4.864	789690	56992	3144.1	1.6	4.5
3	Kanamycin	4.863	790187	56962	3118.1	1.6	4.5
4	Kanamycin	4.862	791763	56934	3147.3	1.6	4.5
5	Kanamycin	4.862	794118	57105	3101.8	1.6	4.5
Mean			790597.2		3118.5	1.6	4.5
Std. Dev.			2553.9				
% RSD			0.3				

Peak Name :cephalexin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu V \cdot sec$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	cephalexin	3.517	520512	55970	3743.5	1.5
2	cephalexin	3.514	521717	56909	3777.3	1.5
3	cephalexin	3.513	521846	57014	3776.0	1.5
4	cephalexin	3.514	522710	56972	3822.2	1.5
5	cephalexin	3.514	523284	56798	3770.1	1.5
Mean			522013.9		3777.8	1.5
Std. Dev.			1057.0			
% RSD			0.2			

The Method precision study was performed for the %RSD of kanamycin and cephalixin was found to be 0.7 and 0.8(NMT 2).

Intermediate precision/Ruggedness

The intermediate precision study was performed for five injections of kanamycin and cephalixin. Each standard injection was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each standard injection was used for calculation of % RSD. The chromatograms are shown in Fig. and results are tabulated below

Chromatograms showing intermediate precision injections-1to 5

Showing results for intermediate precision 1 of kanamycin and cephalixin

Peak Name : kanamycin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	kanamycin	4.863	790742	56569	3075.9	1.6	4.5
2	kanamycin	4.860	794791	56512	3043.2	1.7	4.5
3	kanamycin	4.862	796445	56415	3029.9	1.6	4.4
Mean			793992.9		3049.7	1.6	4.5
Std. Dev.			2934.1				
% RSD			0.4				

Peak Name : cephalixin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	cephalexin	3.513	521817	56358	3704.2	1.6
2	cephalexin	3.515	522684	56384	3696.0	1.5
3	cephalexin	3.516	522921	56456	3716.3	1.5
Mean			522473.9		3705.5	1.6
Std. Dev.			581.3			
% RSD			0.1			

Showing results for intermediate precision 2 of kanamycin and cephalixin

Peak Name:kanamycin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	kanamycin	4.863	790947	56665	3097.3	1.6	4.5
2	kanamycin	4.863	791835	56696	3066.2	1.7	4.5
3	kanamycin	4.862	792125	56645	3083.0	1.7	4.5
	Mean		791635.7		3082.2	1.6	4.5
	Std. Dev.		613.4				
	% RSD		0.1				

Peak Name: cephalixin

	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	cephalexin	3.515	522263	56267	3713.3	1.5
2	cephalexin	3.514	523696	56496	3753.0	1.6
3	cephalexin	3.516	523942	56039	3720.2	1.6
	Mean		523300.4		3728.8	1.6
	Std. Dev.		906.8			
	% RSD		0.2			

The intermediate precision was performed for %RSD of kanamycin and cephalixin was found to be 0.5 and 0.5 respectively (NMT 2).

Detection limit:

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$\text{Formula: LOD} = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where σ - Standard deviation (SD) S - Slope

The LOD was performed for kanamycin and cephalalexin was found to be 2.17 and 0.0372 respectively.

Quantitation limit:

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

$$\text{Formula: LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where σ - Standard deviation, S - Slope

The LOQ was performed for kanamycin and cephalalexin was found to be 6.60 and 0.112 respectively.

Robustness:

The robustness was performed for the flow rate variations from 0.4ml/min to 0.6ml/min and mobile phase ratio variation from more organic phase to less organic phase ratio for kanamycin and cephalalexin. The method is robust only in less flow condition and the method is robust even by change in the Mobile phase $\pm 5\%$. The chromatograms are shown in Fig. and results are tabulated below

Chromatogram showing more flow rate 0.8ml/min

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Cephalexin	3.201	481064	54727		1.82	3657	1
2	Kanamycin	4.431	729496	55125	4.42	1.91	3032	1

Chromatogram showing less flow rate 1.2 ml/min

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	3.906	584732	56135		1.82	3696	1
2	Kanamycin	5.423	884751	56302	4.52	1.88	3108	1

The results are summarized on evaluation of the above results, it can be concluded that the variation in flow rate affected the method significantly. Hence it indicates that the method is robust even by change in the flow rate ± 0.2 ml/min. The method is robust only in less flow condition.

Showing system suitability results for Cephalexin

S. No	Flow rate (ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	3657	1.8
2	1	3654	1.7
3	1.2	3696	1.8

Showing system suitability results for cephalixin

S.No	Flow rate (ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	3032	1.8
2	1	3320	1.3
3	1.2	3108	1.9

Chromatogram showing more organic phase ratio

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Cephalexin	3.048	496347	57538		1.86	3627	1
2	Kanamycin	3.915	730763	63650	3.47	1.93	3220	1

Chromatogram showing less organic phase ratio

Peak Results

	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	cephalexin	2.914	480253	60472		1.75	3706	1
2	Kanamycin	3.512	734198	72421	2.59	1.86	3309	1

On evaluation of the above results, it can be concluded that the variation in $\pm 5\%$. Organic composition in the mobile phase affected the method significantly. Hence it indicates that the method is robust even by change in the mobile phase $\pm 5\%$.

Showing system suitability results for Cephalexin

S.No	Change in organic composition in the mobile phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	5 % less	3706	1.8
2	*Actual	3745	1.7
3	5 % more	3627	1.8

Showing system suitability results for Kanamycin

S.No	Change in organic composition in the mobile phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	5 % less	3309	1.8
2	*Actual	3254	1.8
3	5 % more	3220	1.9

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A novel method were recognized for simultaneous estimation of Kanamycin and Cephalexin by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were effectively developed for the separation of Kanamycin and Cephalexin by means of SYMMETRYC18 column (4.6×150mm)5 μ , flow rate were 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio were (70:30 v/v) methanol: phosphate buffer (KH₂PO₄ and K₂HPO₄) pH 3 (pH were accustomed with orthophosphoric acid), detection wavelength were 258nm.

The instrument utilizing were WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.403 mins and 3.907mins. The % purity of Kanamycin and Cephalexin were established to be 100.27% and 99.87% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Kanamycin and Cephalexin such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 2294, 1.27 and 4891 and 1.03, the resolution were found to be 8.67. The analytical method were validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study n Kanamycin and Cephalexin were found in concentration range of 50 μ g-250 μ g and 5 μ g-50 μ g and correlation coefficient (r²) were found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery were found to be 99.56% and 99.48%, %RSD for repeatability were 0.27 and 0.40, % RSD for intermediate precision were 0.27 and 0.94 respectively. The precision study were precise, robust, and repeatable. LOD value were 2.17 and 6.60, and LOQ value were 0.032 and 0.1125 respectively.

Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be utilizing for routine analysis of Kanamycin and Cephalexin in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

REFERENCE:

- Herman G, Bergman A, Liu F, Stevens C, Wang A, Zeng W, Chen L, Snyder K, Hilliard D, Tanen M, Tanaka W, Meehan A, Lasseter K, Dilzer S, Blum R, Wagner J. Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamic effects of the oral DPP-4 inhibitor sitagliptin in middle-aged obese subjects. *J.Clin.Pharmacol.*2006; 46 (8): 876–886.
- K. G. Patelet *al***, High-Performance Liquid Chromatographic Determination of Cefalexin Monohydrate and Kanamycin Monosulfate with Precolumn Derivatization. *Journal of Liquid Chromatography & Related Technologies* Volume 38, Issue 6, 2015
- Patel satish.A *et al***, Spectrophotometric Determination Of Cephalexin Using Ninhydrin Reagent In Tablet Dosage Form. *Patel satish A et al. IRJP* 2011,2(9),123-126
- A. Vyasa *et al***, Development and Validation of Spectrophotometric Method for Estimation of Cephalexin in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Forms. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry* 2011, Vol. 27, No. (1): Pg. 359-362
- Nandan V. Shinde *et al***, Development and Validation of HPTLC Method for Estimation of Cephalexin in Human Plasma. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences* ISSN: 2229-3701
- Sagar Suman PANDA *et al***, Determination of Cephalexin Monohydrate in Pharmaceutical

- Dosage Form by Stability-Indicating RP-UFLC and UV Spectroscopic Methods. *Scientia pharmaceutica* 2013; 81: 1029–1041
7. **J Vijay et al.**, Formulation And Evaluation Of Cephalexin Extended-Release Matrix Tablets Using Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose As Rate-Controlling Polymer. *J Young Pharm.* 2012 Jan-Mar; 4(1): 3–12
 8. **Kalpana G. Patel et al.**, Derivative and ratio derivative spectroscopic methods for simultaneous determination of Cefalexin monohydrate and Kanamycin monosulphate using phenylisocyanate as derivatizing reagent. *Kalpana G. Patel et al. / Journal of Pharmacy Research* 2014,8(5),689-695
 9. **Kaale E et al.**, Development And Validation Of A Simple Capillary Zone Electrophoresis Method For The Analysis Of Kanamycin Sulfate With UV Detection After Pre-Capillary Derivatization. **J Chromatogr A. 2001 Jul 27;924(1-2):451-8**
 10. Tripathi K.D. *Essential of Medical Pharmacology*, 5th Edn, Jaypee Brothers Medical publisher New Delhi. pp: 515-516.